

Potential Biologically Active Agents: VIII. Synthesis of 2-Methyl (and Styryl)-3-Aryl-4-(3H)-Quinazolones

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Acetantranil and aminobenzoic acids have been condensed to yield seven 2-methyl-3-aryl-4-(3H)-quinazolones. Some of these quinazolones have been condensed with aromatic aldehydes to furnish corresponding 2-styryl analogs. The compounds thus synthesised have been evaluated for their inhibitory effect against bacteria.

QUINAZOLONES have been reported to be biologically versatile compounds having antimarial^{1,2}, antiviral^{3,4}, antibacterial⁵, anti-tubercular⁶, hypnotic⁷⁻⁹, anticonvulsant¹⁰, antipyretic¹¹, analgesic¹¹, antiinflammatory¹¹, diuretic¹² and antihypertensive^{13,14} activities. In view of these observations it was considered of interest to synthesise a series of new quinazolones (I and II) incorporating *para* aminobenzoic acid (PABA) or its alkyl esters. PABA is required for the synthesis of folic acid (III) by the microorganisms. I and II having PABA moiety incorporated in their structures might interfere with the synthesis of III and thereby inhibit the growth of the microorganisms.

The synthesis of I has been accomplished by condensing acetantranil, obtained by treating anthranilic acid with acetic anhydride with aminobenzoic acids and their alkyl esters. Condensation of I with aromatic aldehydes yielded II. During the synthesis of I it was observed that I could also be

obtained by fusion of N-acetylanthranilic acid with aminobenzoates. The products obtained from N-acetylanthranilic acid and acetantranil were identical.

Reaction of acetantranil with 4-*n*-propyl/*n*-butyl-aminobenzoates yielded a highly viscous gummy material from which a crystalline solid product could not be isolated. The viscous mass was therefore directly treated with an aldehyde to furnish the corresponding styryl derivatives.

Isomeric *o*-amino and *m*-aminobenzoic acids and their alkyl esters have also been utilised for the synthesis of quinazolones with a view to establish their effect on the biological activity.

Several I and II thus synthesised are listed in Tables 1 and 2. All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses. Further support for their structures was obtained from an examination of their infrared, n.m.r. and mass spectra.

TABLE 1—2-METHYL-3-ARYL-4-(3H)-QUINAZOLONES(I)

S.No.	R	M.P. °C	Mol. formula	%Analyses		Yield %	
				Calcd.	Found		
1.	2-COOH	258—259	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃ ·H ₂ O	C,	64.43	64.34	45
				H,	4.73	4.79	
				N,	9.39	9.29	
2.	2-COOCH ₃	260	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₃ ·H ₂ O	C,	65.34	64.58	50
				H,	5.15	4.80	
				N,	8.97	9.39	
3.	3-COOH	286	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃	C,	68.57	68.50	55
				H,	4.31	4.78	
				N,	9.99	9.77	
4.	3-COOCH ₃ ^{d,e}	145—146	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₃	C,	69.37	68.86	60
				H,	4.79	4.96	
				N,	9.52	9.37	
5.	4-COOH	293	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃	C,	68.57	68.85	55
				H,	4.31	4.74	
				N,	9.99	9.68	
6.	4-COOCH ₃ ^{b,d}	183—184	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₃	C,	69.37	68.70	65
				H,	4.79	5.35	
				N,	9.52	9.31	
7.	4-COOC ₂ H ₅ ^{c,a}	172—173	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃	—	—	70	

^a, Lit.¹⁵ m.p. 174°–175°. I.R. (μ): *b*, 5.80 (C = O, ester), 5.87 (C = O, ring); *c*, 5.75 (C = O, ester), 5.82 (C = O, ring). Mass spectra; *d*, *m/e* 294(M⁺), *m/e* 279 (M–CH₃), *m/e* 263 (M–OCH₃), *m/e* 235 (M–COOCH₃). NMR; *e*, δ 2.06(2-CH₃), δ 3.85(COOCH₃), δ 7.50–8.20 (aromatic 8H).

Infrared spectra of compounds 6 and 7 (Table 1) showed characteristic absorptions due to ester and ring carbonyl groups. Compounds 5, 12, 14 (Table 2) showed absorptions due to styryl groups in addition to peaks due to carbonyl groups. In the n.m.r. spectrum of compound 4 (Table 1) the olefinic methyl signal appeared at δ 2.06 (singlet). A three proton singlet at δ 3.85 has been assigned to COOCH₃. A multiplet integrating for eight aromatic protons was observed between δ 7.50 to 8.20.

Mass spectra of compounds 4 and 6 (Table 1) yielded identical fragmentation patterns. The molecular ion peak appeared at *m/e* 294 (100%). The peak at *m/e* 279 (91%) corresponded to the loss of the 2-methyl radical. The peaks at *m/e* 263 (20%) and *m/e* 235 (15%) have been attributed to successive loss of methoxy and carbomethoxy groups.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were taken on a Perkin-Elmer 137 Spectrophotometer in KBr discs. The n.m.r. spectra were recorded on a Varian A60D Spectrometer in dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) using hexamethyldisilazane as an internal standard, while mass spectra were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer Hitachi RMU6E Mass Spectrometer.

Acetantranil¹⁵, m.p. 80° was prepared by refluxing anthranilic acid (1 mole) and acetic anhydride (2 moles) for 1 hr under anhydrous conditions. Excess of acetic anhydride was distilled off and the solid mass thus obtained was used for the synthesis of quinazolones without further purification.

Alkylaminobenzoates were prepared by refluxing an aminobenzoic acid (20 g.), thionylchloride (20 ml) and an appropriate alcohol (200 ml) for 12 hr and working up the reaction mixture.

2-Methyl-3-aryl-4-(3H)-quinazolones (I) (Table 1).

Method A: Acetantranil (0.01 mole) and aminobenzoic acid or its alkyl ester (0.01 mole) were intimately mixed and heated on a free flame for 5 min. with vigorous shaking. To the hot reaction mixture 20 ml of ethanol was added and the contents of the flask were allowed to cool. Scratching the sides with a glass rod yielded a crystalline solid which was recrystallised from ethanol.

Method B: N-Acetylanthranilic acid (0.01 mole) and an alkylaminobenzoate (0.01 mole) were heated together on a free flame for 5 min. Working up the reaction mixture as described under A gave the desired product in good yield. All the compounds of Table 1 were synthesised according to A. Compounds 6 and 7 were also prepared by Method B. The products obtained by both methods were checked for their identity by determining their mixed m.p.s. and by comparison of their infrared spectra which were identical.

2-Styryl-3-aryl-4-(3H)-quinazolones (II)

A mixture of 2-methyl-3-aryl-4-(3H)-quinazolone (I) (0.01 mole) and 0.01 mole of an appropriate aldehyde were heated in 20 ml of glacial acetic acid for 2 hr. The contents of the reaction vessel were then cooled and the solid product thus separated

TABLE 2—2-STYRYL-3-ARYL-4-(3H)-QUINAZOLONES(II)

S.No.	R	Ar	M.P. °C	Mol. formula	%Analyses		Yield %
					Calcd.	Found	
1.	4-COOCH ₃	Ph	240	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃ ·½H ₂ O	C, 73.64 H, 4.89 N, 7.15	73.07 4.82 7.05	65
2.	4-COOCH ₃	4-HOC ₆ H ₄	>250	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄	C, 72.35 H, 4.55 N, 7.03	72.22 4.85 6.99	70
3.	4-COOCH ₃	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	240	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄	C, 72.80 H, 4.88 N, 6.79	72.51 5.01 6.61	75
4.	4-COOCH ₃	3-HOC ₆ H ₄	>232	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄	C, 72.35 H, 4.55 N, 7.03	72.15 4.76 6.97	65
5.	4-COOCH ₃ ^b	2-HOC ₆ H ₄	>240	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄	C, 72.35 H, 4.55 N, 7.03	72.07 4.79 6.84	55
6.	4-COOCH ₃	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	215—220 ^d	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₃ ·½H ₂ O	C, 71.88 H, 5.56 N, 9.67	71.89 5.71 9.64	50
7.	4-COOCH ₃	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	215—216	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅	C, 67.44 H, 4.01 N, 9.83	66.86 4.20 9.56	60
8.	4-COOCH ₃	4-CH(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	133	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₃	C, 76.40 H, 5.69 N, 6.60	75.62 6.06 6.41	60
9.	4-COOCH ₃	2-furyl	217 ^a	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄	C, 70.98 H, 4.33 N, 7.52	70.47 4.51 7.36	65
10.	4-COOCH ₃	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	233—235	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅ ·½H ₂ O	C, 66.04 H, 4.15 N, 9.62	66.04 4.02 9.58	75
11.	4-COOC ₃ H ₇ ⁿ	2-HOC ₆ H ₄	231	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₄	C, 73.23 H, 5.20 N, 6.57	73.57 5.48 6.56	55
12.	4-COOC ₄ H ₉ ⁿ	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ ^c	181	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₄	C, 73.98 H, 5.76 N, 6.16	74.10 6.04 6.13	65
13.	3-COOCH ₃	2-HOC ₆ H ₄	>244	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄	C, 72.35 H, 4.55 N, 7.03	71.46 4.65 6.89	70
14.	3-COOCH ₃ ^d	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	168—170	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄	C, 72.80 H, 4.88 N, 6.79	72.31 4.67 6.73	

^a, recrystallised from acetic acid-water. I.R. : (μ); ^b, 3.00(OH), 5.77(C = O, ester), 6.00(C = O, ring), 6.10(styryl); ^c, 5.80(C = O, ester), 5.90(C = O, ring), 6.05(styryl); ^d, 5.75(C = O, ester), 5.90(C = O, ring), 6.10(styryl).

was filtered and recrystallised from a suitable solvent.

The analytical and other pertinent data are recorded in Table 2.

Biological Data

The compounds reported in Tables 1 and 2 were screened for their antibacterial activity against four different microorganisms: *Bacillus megaterium*, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Salmonella typhosa* by agar diffusion technique¹⁶. None of the compounds showed any significant activity. Only moderate inhibition was observed against *B. megaterium* in case of compounds 8 and 14 (Table 2). Bacterial cultures maintained at C.D.R.I., Lucknow were used.

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